

Effect of Enterprise Resource Planning in Supply Chain Management Module on the Performance of County Governments

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to establish the effect of ERP in supply chain management module on the performance of County governments in North Rift Economic Bloc (NOREB). The study is informed by Institutional Theory (Transaction Cost Economics). The study employed explanatory. The study targeted 1,640 permanent employees from ICT and finance ministries from six counties in the North Rift region in Kenya. These included: Nandi, Uasin Gishu, Elgeyo Marakwet, Trans Nzoia, Baringo and West Pokot Counties. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select a representative sample of 321 employees in the ICT and revenue departments from the six County governments. The findings in have showed that integration of ERP in the SC module has a positive and significant effect on county performance ($\beta_1 = 0.102, p = 0.01$) Thus, the study inferred that ERP in SCM key determinants in performance of county government. Therefore, the study recommends that all the departments in the organization that are yet to be integrated should be integrated to reap the benefits of integration. The study also recommends that all public organizations should adopt ERP with the aim of improving their efficiency

Keywords: Supply chain management, ERP, performance, County governments

Introduction

Performance is the focus of any business or organization and only through performance are organizations able to grow and progress (Gavrea *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, the survival of a business is to accomplish set goals and objectives (Muduenyi *et al.*, 2015). To improve business performance, organizations require an efficient planning and control system that synchronizes planning of all processes across the organization. According to Baheshti (2011) ERP systems successfully enhance efficiency and improve overall performance of an organization upon adoption. Over the years, corporations have adopted new technology to integrate business activities in order to achieve both effectiveness and efficiency in their operations. In recent years, many firms locally and internally have invested on ERP systems in order to integrate all business activities into a uniform platform. The implementation of ERP system enables the firm to reduce the transaction costs of the business and improve its productivity, customer satisfaction and profitability. Maiyo (2016) in her study on the influence of Enterprise Resource Planning system in enhancing service delivery and performance of procurement function confirmed that ERP system played a key role.

In Maiyo (2016) study on the confirmed early finding of a research carried on Taiwanese IT firms. It also provides empirical evidence that the beneficial impacts of 2 ERP systems on the supply chain do lead to better overall supply chain management (SCM) and performance. Due to increasing global competition in a dynamic business setting, many project managers are now aware of the benefits of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems (Chang 2011).

This may suggest the need to establish whether the use of ERPs have positively affected the performance of the organization. In particular, it may be useful to establish if the intended effects have occurred given the reported failure rates in the literature. The literature indicates these projects as highly risky with a relatively low success rate (Zhang *et al.*, 2005). For instance, Magnusson *et al.* (2004) report a rate of 90 percent, Kovacic and Bosilj-Vuksic (2005) report a 89-91 percent, Martin (1998), a 90 percent, Umble and Umble (2002) report a 50-75

percent, Zhang *et al.* (2003) report a 67-90 percent, Sarkis and Sundarraj (2003) report a two-third failure rate. While these studies report different failure rates, it is suggestive of the need to examine whether the effect of ERPs, on business processes of public organizations has been positive or not. Perhaps the findings on the impact of ERPs from research in previous work that has tended to focus on the factors that influence the success of ERPs, may not adequately explain their use and impact on business processes in the public organizations, such as county governments.

While research on ERPs has tended to focus on success factors in the context of manufacturing firms, not much has been documented on their effect on the performance of public organizations. It is not known whether the implementation of the ERP at county governments has affected positively or negatively on the business processes as no study has been undertaken in this respect. A need therefore exists for a study that can improve our understanding of the effect of ERP in supply chain management module. The current study fills this gap by examining the effect of ERPs has on the performance county governments in NOREB. Thus, the study hypothesized that;

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of ERP in supply chain management on the performance of County governments

Theoretical Framework

Institutional theory asserts that the development of formal structures in firms can significantly be influenced by the institutional environment (Scott, 2014). For example, Ugrin (2009) incorporates institutional theory into ERP systems adoption in his study. Ugrin mentions that institutional theory suggests that a firm deals with uncertainty, look beyond traditional cost-benefit analyses and look also to institutional factors to legitimize their decisions. Ugrin examines the role of institutional factors in addition to traditional decision variables inexperienced managers' decisions whether or not to adopt ERP systems.

Transaction cost economics is an important concept of institutional theory and several studies pay attention to this concept. For example, Poston and Grabski (2001) use this theory to develop hypothesis regarding the examination of how ERP systems affect firm's transaction costs. According to them, "transaction cost economics posits that a firm is an economic entity created in an effort to economize on market transaction costs, for example searching and communicating market information, negotiating a deal, and preventing or dealing with contract default" (p. 278). Transaction costs are usually high when, for example, a firm has to deal with firm-specific assets and a long-term contract is necessary to prevent the opportunistic behavior of the other party (Williamson, 1981). Furthermore, Hyvönen (2003) mention that findings of previous studies indicate that ERP systems are effective with regard to transaction processing and thus lead to a reduction of the transaction costs of operations.

Literature Review

Integrating ERP into a supply chain management (SCM) department allows the organization to reduce its dependency on human effort and eliminates the need to maintain a number of scattered and distinct systems. The global success of enterprise resource planning has captured the interest of business, information technology, and information systems researchers. Companies have spent billions of dollars buying and implementing enterprise resource planning exploring the rationales for ERP and SCM integration. Nonetheless, companies have been able to achieve measurable, positive returns on ERP investments. But despite the many benefits of ERP-SCM integration, some companies are lagging behind for several reasons. This is mainly due to the initial investment to acquire and implement an ERP system. This investment is substantial and even after

the system is up and running, the costs continue to mount (Business Intelligence Center 2012), this keeps many organizations from implementing ERP software.

Information system that integrates the ERP system to logistics chain provides a competitive advantage (Akkermans *et al.*, 2003). ERP systems and SCM practices are the basis for organizational performance and ongoing competitive advantage. SCM provides effective tools for institutions and helps to meet the needs of suppliers and customers, and competitors. ERP systems replace complex and sometimes manual interfaces between different systems with standardized, cross-functional transaction automation. Order cycle times (the time from when an order is placed until the product or service is delivered) can be reduced, resulting in improved throughput, customer response times, and delivery speeds (Cotteleer and Bendoly, 2006). According to Hunton *et al.* (2003), ERP system provides major changes in culture and behavior models which are the main sources of economic advantages. ERP systems success (synonymous with ERP success) refers to the use of such systems to enhance organizational effectiveness (Gable, Chan, 2003; Ifinedo, 2006a), which is different from the technical implementation success of such systems wherein measurement indicators such as cost overruns, project management metrics, and time estimates are the main concerns.

E-Supply Chain Management (E-SCM) uses the advances of technology made available through the advancement of the internet to further simplify SCM by utilizing it to simplify the flow of information to different members of the supply chain, thus, further making SCM more efficient and much easier. Through this, a supply chain can share crucial information in real-time. The use of the internet in information sharing will better reflect decisions from all spheres of the business in and out as it also facilitates information sharing and collaboration according to Gimenez and Lourenco (2004). Also from Gimenez and Lourenco (2004), it can be seen that the primary effect of E-SCM to organizations is that the internal value chain is improved as well because of information sharing and collaboration. Functional and business units are able to improve customer relationship management and customer service management as a result (Gimenez & Lourenco, 2004). Supply chain business process integration involves collaborative work between buyers and suppliers, joint product development, common systems and shared information. According to Lambert and Cooper (2000), operating an integrated supply chain requires a continuous information flow. Lambert (2004) stated that SCM and E-SCM are crucial features for a successful ERP since the flow and information sharing is important for the business to function. SCM requires the management of materials and information flow in the whole chain, from suppliers through to customers.

A successful organization must be able to manage the integration of its business, technologies, processes, departments and people within the enterprise itself and across extended enterprises (Awad & Nassar, 2010). The integration inside any business organization includes not only integrating ERP systems with legacy systems to ensure an effective and efficient communications between these systems, but also include the integration of ERP systems with SCM systems and linking it with CRM systems to encourage the cooperation and collaboration across the entire value chain (Awad & Nassar, 2010).

Due to the rapid evolution in information and communication technologies (ICT), the traditional supply chain management processes have been enhanced to be integrated with different business processes for the purpose of increase the overall value of the chain, reduce cost, improve production process and compete with different business environments. As discussed in the earlier sections of this document, ERP effectively integrates all the information which is required for the business to operate including finance, accounting, production, human resources, quality management, sales and marketing. We can see that ERP is an integrated information system which integrates the internal working process of the organization, standardize the internal procedures for data processing and combines all the operations data which are generated by multiple departments or functions (Adaileh & Abu-alganam, 2010). On the other hand, Supply Chain Management (SCM) is the management of upstream and downstream to increase the value of the chain. It looks at the business as a chain of well

integrated and connected entities which will add more value, reduce inventory, reduce lead time and reduce cost. The following table illustrates comparison between ERP and SCM which will help to understand how to build relationship and integrate these two systems (Tarn & Beaumont, 2002).

Literature and Gaps

Enterprise resource planning has been found to impact positively of the performance of organizations through the integration of various departmental information. ERP has been found to result into tangible and non-tangible benefits which help sustain operational efficiencies in the long run. However, studies have also demonstrated that not all ERP adoptions will lead to improved performance of the organization. ERP systems have been found to perform better in transaction processing and enhancement of decision making process as the departments are able to share the common data and practices across the enterprise. While these studies highlight the important of ERP in organizational performance, these studies were mainly done in the private sector whose goals are profit making. There is however no study done on the effect of ERP adoption on the performance of public organizations hence a knowledge gap. This study seeks to determine the effect of ERP system of the performance of County Governments.

Material and methods

The study was explanatory in nature and sought to establish the perception of managerial and non-managerial users of ERP in SCM system on performance of county government. The study targeted 1,640 permanent employees from ICT and finance ministries from six counties in the North Rift region in Kenya. These included: Nandi, Uasin Gishu, Elgeyo Marakwet, Trans Nzoia, Baringo and West Pokot Counties. Taro Yamane (1973) sample size formula and modified by Kent, (2008) was used to select a sample size of 321 employees in the ICT and revenue. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 321 sampled employees. The study collected primary data using a structured questionnaire and included questions on a five-point Likert-type eliciting respondents' perception on the extent of the effect of ERP systems on business process. To measure the reliability, the Cronbach Alpha technique was employed. A Cronbach's Coefficient alpha of 0.743 was computed for the four independent variables based on data collected to test the reliability as shown below. When high coefficient is seen, it implies that the factors tested are valid and consistent in measuring the concept, (Dawson, 2002).

Model Specification

In addition, to further determine the power of the study model, the study regressed the variables using Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The study also used Pearson's Moment Correlation to test the association between variables.

OLS regression model

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

$Y_{(i,t)}$ - Is the performance of the County Governments

β_0 - Is the constant

X_1 - ERP in SCM

β_1 , - Coefficients

ε_i - Is the residual error

All the above statistical tests were used with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS), version 20. All tests were two-tailed. Significant levels were measured at 95% confidence level with significant differences recorded at $p < 0.05$

FINDINGS

The study distributed 321 questionnaires to the respondents and 249 questionnaires were returned giving a response rate of 78% and ascertained to be complete. This response rate was acceptable since according to Fowler (2002), the whole point of conducting a survey is to obtain useful, reliable, and valid data in a format that makes it possible to analyze and draw conclusions about the total target population.

Descriptive Statistics

Integration of ERP into the supply chain management process is a critical component in ensuring error reduction and involves various components such as information technology that brings in the aspect of innovation for efficiency. The study thus sought to assess the level of integration of ERP into the supply chain management module of the various departments in the County government basing on the perspective of the employees who are the users of the ERP system and the findings were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Supply Chain Management Module

N=249	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
ERP make it easier to establish and alter the parameters within which a supply chain is required to operate.	2.97	1.079	-0.235	-0.760
The county use ERP to handle procurement and supply of the goods, services and other resources that are needed across the supply chain	2.96	1.308	-0.212	-1.205
The county uses ERP to ability to monitor, review and alter supply chain efforts and activities in real-time to ensure cost-effective operations	2.99	1.132	-0.455	-1.045
The county uses ERP to track orders and fulfill them when necessary	2.88	1.45	-0.139	-1.343
ERP provides complete visibility across the supply chain network which is highly impossible in the manual process	3.10	1.384	-0.281	-1.179
ERP helps organization to have a control over all the suppliers and distributors	2.92	1.253	-0.038	-0.97
ERP connect all the members across the network can share vital information like demand, forecasting reports, inventory levels, status of production, transportation plans and many more in real time	3.37	1.415	-0.554	-1.077
SC module	3.482	0.763	-0.603	0.061

From the findings in Table 4.2 a mean of less than 1.5 means strong disagreement with the statement, greater than 1.5 but less than 2.5 means disagreement, greater than 2.5 but less than 3.5 means neutral, greater than 3.5 to 4.5 means agreement while more than 4.5 to 5.0 means strong agreement. The findings show that majority of the employees expressed a neutral perspective regarding the ERP making it easier to establish and alter the parameters within which a supply chain is required to operate, mean = 2.97 (SD = 1.079). This means that the employees were not well versed with how the ERP can be used in making it easier and alter some constraints of supply chain management showing less capacity. Furthermore, majority of the employees were neutral with the statement that the County uses ERP to handle procurement and supply of the goods, services and other resources that are needed across the supply chain, mean = 2.96 (SD = 1.308). These findings show that although the ERP exist at the county departments, it is not integrated in departments such as procurement and supply of

goods thereby showing that there are existing inefficiencies within the current procurement and supply of goods processes that would otherwise be improved by the integration of the ERP system.

The findings also show that majority of the employees were neutral about the statement that the county uses ERP ability to monitor, review and alter supply chain efforts and activities in real-time to ensure cost-effective operations, mean = 2.99 (SD = 1.132). This shows that the county to a significant extent is denied the benefit of having cost-effective operations because of the lack of integration of the ERP system. Majority of the employees were also neutral with the statement that the county uses ERP to track orders and fulfill them when necessary, mean = 2.88 (SD = 1.450) showing that the county also faces challenges in integration of ERP in tracking of orders and fulfilling such orders.

Furthermore, the findings also showed that majority of the employees were neutral with the statement that ERP provides complete visibility across the supply chain network which is highly impossible in the manual process, mean = 3.10 (SD = 1.384) and indicates that since there is incomplete integration, the manual process is still used to a certain extent. The findings also show that majority of the employees were neutral with the statement that ERP helps organization to have a control over all the suppliers and distributors, mean = 2.92 (SD = 1.253) while majority also were neutral with the statement that ERP connect all the members across the network can share vital information like demand, forecasting reports, inventory levels, status of production, transportation plans and many more in real time, mean = 3.37 (SD = 1.415) that shows challenges in terms of reporting, analysis of reports as well as other critical processes. The mean response was 3.482 (SD = 0.763) showing that majority of the employees were not sure of the level of integration of the ERP system within the supply chain management processes of majority of the departments at the County. The pinnacle of the implementation of any system within an organization can only be visualized in the performance of the organization in various areas. Given that county governments are public entities; the core stakeholder is the citizen of the county. It is thus the responsibility of the various departments at the county governments to ensure that they are able to meet the expectations of the public in various areas. Performance in this case was measured based on the capacity of the departments under the county government to deliver projects and their returns, timeliness, quality of service, budget lines, efficiency and effectiveness, reduction of corruption and the address of social, economic and technical performance goals. Thus, the study sought to establish the perspectives of the employees regarding county performance in the various areas given the level of integration and integration of the ERP system in the various management modules and the findings were presented in Table 4.6.

Table 2: County Performance

N=249	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
The county has successfully implemented Projects within set out budget limits.	3.32	0.984	-0.467	-0.105
The county projects meet their technical or social performance goals.	3.44	1.034	-0.582	-0.351
Projects implemented meet their schedule objectives.	3.43	0.873	-0.820	0.251
Counties' project portfolio has an excellent balance of projects.	3.36	1.204	-0.586	-0.367
Most of the projects implemented provide good returns	3.47	1.024	-0.349	-0.167
The customers are served fast	3.82	1.053	-0.908	0.126
The level of corruption in the ministry has been minimized	3.82	1.053	-0.908	0.126
The payment of the suppliers are processed on time	3.84	1.072	-0.892	0.18
The quality of services to the county citizen has improved	3.57	0.710	-1.289	2.651
There is no more time wasting in locating files	3.55	0.975	-0.328	-0.268
Revenue has gone up	3.33	0.869	-0.183	0.311
Cost of operations have gone down	3.50	0.853	-0.683	0.136
County performance	3.70	0.562	-2.122	5.375

The findings in Table 4.6 show that majority of the employees in various departments in the county governments agree that the customers are served fast and the level of corruption in the ministry has been minimized, mean = 3.82 (SD = 1.053) respectively. In addition, majority of the employees agree that: the payment of the suppliers is processed on time, mean = 3.84 (SD = 1.072), the quality of services to the county citizens has improved, mean = 3.57 (SD = 0.710), there is no more time wasting in locating files, mean = 3.55 (SD = 0.975) and cost of operations have gone down, mean = 3.50 (SD = 0.853). These findings show that because of the integration of the ERP, there have been improvements in the level and quality of customer service, reduction in corruption and wastage. However, there were challenges noted in terms of performance of the county in certain areas since majority of the employees were not sure whether: the county has successfully implemented projects within set out budget limits, mean = 3.32 (SD = 0.984), the county projects meet their technical or social performance goals, mean = 3.44 (SD = 1.034), projects implemented meet their schedule objectives, mean = 3.43 (SD = 0.873), county's project portfolio has an excellent balance of projects, mean = 3.36 (SD = 1.204), most of the projects implemented provide good returns, mean = 3.47 (SD = 1.024) and whether revenue has gone up, mean = 3.33 (SD = 0.869). This essentially shows that there are challenges in the integration and implementation of the ERP system despite the system having increased performance in certain areas in the county departments. Overall, the mean response was 3.70 (SD = 0.562) that shows that majority of the employees had the view that county performance has increased given the integration of the ERP system in the functions of various departments in the county government.

Hypotheses Testing

Correlation and regression analysis is critical in any research undertaking. a correlation analysis of the independent factors and the dependent factor (county performance) was conducted and the findings were summarized and presented in Table 3. From the findings in Table 4.9, the relationship between the SC module and county performance was found to be positive and significant, $\rho = 0.477$, p -value < 0.001 indicating that there is 47.7% probability that the county's performance will increase with increased integration of the ERP system in the SC module. The regression model was developed in order to enable the testing of the study hypothesis with the aim of providing answers to the achievement of the study objectives. First the model summary was assessed by examining the amount of variation accounted for by the model as well as the analysis of the variance. Later the model was assessed by examining the estimated regression coefficients. The results in Table 3 showed that all the predictors explain 69.8% of the variation in county performance (R-squared = 0.698, Adjusted R-squared = 0.693). The study findings in Table 3 indicated that the above discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of F (4, 244) value 141.228 ($p < 0.05$) showing that the model was fit in predicting any change in county performance.

Table 3: Estimated Regression Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			correlation partial r
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
(Constant)	1.295	0.107		12.093	0	
SC module	0.067	0.027	0.102	2.46	0.015	0.677**
R		0.836a				
R Square		0.698				
Adjusted R Square		0.693				
Std. Error of the Estimate		0.311				
F Stat	141.228					
Sig. F	0.000					

a Dependent Variable: County performance

The hypothesis (H_{01}) stated that;

There is no significant effect of effect of supply chain management module on the performance of County governments. The findings in Table 3 revealed that integration of ERP in the SC module has a positive and significant effect on county performance, $\beta_1 = 0.102$, $p = 0.015$ and indicating that with each unit increase in the SC module, county performance increases by 0.102 units. This means that the hypothesis is rejected and the conclusion is that a supply chain management module in the departments of the county governments that has integrated ERP system would increase the county performance. Integration of the ERP system is costly for many organizations. Nonetheless, organizations have been able to achieve measurable, positive returns on ERP investments. But despite the many benefits of ERP–SCM integration, some companies are lagging behind for several reasons. This is mainly due to the initial investment to acquire and implement an ERP system. This investment is substantial and even after the system is up and running, the costs continue to mount (Business Intelligence Center 2012), this keeps many organizations from implementing ERP software.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings have also revealed that a supply chain management module that has the ERP system integrated has a positive and significant effect on county performance. Despite this and the benefits highlighted of the ERP system integration, there are gaps that deny the county of the benefit of having cost-effective operations because of the lack of integration of the ERP system. The study established the processes at County Governments are integrated in the system. The study also established that all the departmental information was integrated. The study found that supply functions in the organization were integrated into the system. All the transactions were integrated into the system. The established that the integration of the business processes have to a large extent enhanced the performance of the organization. The study established that most of the processes in the organization have been integrated which has improved the efficiency of the organization. The study recommends that all the departments in the organization that are yet to be integrated should be integrated to reap the benefits of integration. The study also recommends that all public organizations should adopt ERP with the aim of improving their efficiency. The study established that the adoption of ERP has enhanced the generation of timely information for quick decision making purposes. The study recommends that all government departments and agencies should adopt ERP with the aim of enhancing accurate information processing for faster decision making process.

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